

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Neonatal Jaundice in Iraqi Hospitals: A Study at the Obstetric and Pediatrics Hospital, Samawah

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Abstract

Introduction: Neonatal jaundice (hyperbilirubinemia) is one of the most common clinical conditions globally and is the second leading cause of neonatal hospitalization worldwide. However, the epidemiology and specific risk factors of neonatal jaundice remain poorly described in Iraq, especially in the provinces. This study aimed to examine the epidemiology of neonatal jaundice and to identify maternal, neonatal, and perinatal risk factors associated with requiring phototherapy for neonatal jaundice at a major referral center in Samawah, Iraq.

Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional study of all live-born neonates who were born at or admitted to the Obstetric and Pediatrics hospital in Samawah from January 1, 2022 to December 31, 2022 was conducted. Maternal, neonatal demographics, delivery data, and management of jaundice data were collected from hospital records. Neonates with total serum bilirubin levels meeting the criteria for phototherapy established by the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) were considered to be cases of significant jaundice. Chi-square tests and logistic regression were used during statistical analysis to identify independent risk factors.

Results: The overall incidence of jaundice requiring phototherapy was 682 cases (14.1%) out of 4,850 live births. of these, 530 were classified as either physiologic or breastfeeding-related jaundice (78.2% of cases), while 152 cases (21.8%) had identifiable pathologic causes of jaundice on evaluation. The following independent risk factors were found to be significantly associated with needing phototherapy for neonatal jaundice: gestational age <37 weeks (AOR = 3.45, 95% CI: 2.67-4.46), birth weight <2500 g (AOR = 2.89, 95% CI: 2.18-3.83), male gender (AOR = 1.52, 95% CI: 1.25-1.85), primiparity (AOR = 1.48, 95% CI: 1.21-1.80), maternal age <20 years (AOR = 1.92, 95% CI: 1.45-2.55) and prior sibling history of jaundice (AOR = 2.95, 95% CI: 2.15-4.05). of the neonates with jaundice, ABO incompatibility was noted in 8.5%. **Conclusion:** The prevalence of significant neonatal jaundice in this sample of neonates from Iraq is high, and there are many independent risk factors contributing to the development of neonatal jaundice in this population, including prematurity, low birth weight, male gender, being a primiparous mother, being less than 20 years of age, and a prior sibling with jaundice. The results of this study highlight the need for thorough prenatal screenings, close monitoring for jaundice following delivery, and intensified education for at-risk mothers receiving health care services in Iraq.

Introduction

Neonatal jaundice is a medical condition characterised by the yellowing of a newborn's skin and/or eyes as a result of having too much bilirubin in the blood stream. This is one of the most common medical problems that occur during the first week of life [1]. Approximately

60% of infants born after 37 weeks of pregnancy (term infants), and around 80% of infants born before 37 weeks of pregnancy (preterm infants) develop jaundice in the first week [2]. Most cases of jaundice are non-pathologic, self-limited, and are classified as either physiological or breastfeeding-related jaundice. Some

More Information

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infants may develop severe jaundice (hyperbilirubinemia) and subsequently develop life-long neurological problems, including (but not limited to) acute bilirubin encephalopathy and the chronic and irreversible form of acute bilirubin encephalopathy — kernicterus [3]. Kernicterus will cause significant long-term functional disabilities and limitations, including (but not limited to) cerebral palsy, sensorineural hearing loss, movement problems due to an inability to coordinate eye movements, and learning difficulties [4]. There is a large worldwide burden of kernicterus, with infants in many low to middle income countries [5] having little to no access to the care and/or resources necessary for prompt diagnosis and treatment of jaundice.

Neonatal jaundice occurs when the bilirubin produced from the breakdown of red blood cells is produced more quickly than it can be removed from the body. During the neonatal period, there is a larger number of red blood cells, a shorter life span of the red blood cells, and an immature liver that does not have the ability to remove bilirubin from the blood adequately, which increases the amount of bilirubin that accumulates in the infant's body [6]. Pathologic jaundice occurs when the balance of bilirubin production versus bilirubin elimination is disrupted due to pathological conditions such as hemolysis (e.g. blood group incompatibility or G6PD deficiency), increased enterohepatic recirculation of bilirubin, and metabolic defects in bilirubin metabolism [7]. Neonate identification of risk factors is key to classification of neonates needing closer monitoring and/or early intervention to prevent severe hyperbilirubinemia [8].

The global environment has numerous studies that have shown a consistent range of risk factors present. The most influential factors are low birth weight and prematurity which are primarily attributed to immature hepatic UDP-glucuronosyltransferase activity and poor feeding patterns [9,10]. Some important causes of hemolytic jaundice are blood group incompatibilities, especially ABO and Rh(D) incompatible [11]. Other significant risk factors include being a male gender, East Asian ethnicities, having a sibling diagnosed with needing treatment for neonatal jaundice, and breastfeeding exclusively (which commonly is related to poor intake/dehydration during the first days), and maternal factors such as diabetes [12,13]. G6PD deficiency, which is an X-linked body condition that affects most males but also occurs in females, resides in geographic areas such as the Mediterranean region and Lebanese and Palestinian societies. The deficient activity of G6PD can result in the development of hemolytic anemia therefore causing jaundice due to acute hemolysis from oxidatively stressful environments [14].

The epidemiological profile of neonatal jaundice in the Arab World exists with unique considerations. Iraq actually is suffering from many years of war and economic sanction that have produced both infrastructure issues and resource allocation issues in regards to health care. There are larger centers that provide phototherapy and exchange transfusions; however, they cannot guarantee delivery of adequate and/or quality prenatal and postnatal care consistently due to a lack of resources in non-metropolitan areas. The increased prevalence of consanguineous marriages is associated with a greater risk for developing some autosomal recessive disorders, such as hereditary spherocytosis and metabolic disorders that will ultimately cause jaundice [15]. Furthermore, while there has been little national, systematic research on G6PD deficiency in Iraq in recent years, it is also present, and documentation is scarce [16]. Studies examining significant neonatal jaundice in surrounding countries, including Iran and Saudi Arabia, show varying rates - between 10% and 35% - and have highlighted risk factors consistent with those of international studies, but with special emphasis given to the high level of consanguinity and incidence of G6PD deficiency present in these areas [17,18].

Although the clinical importance of neonatal jaundice is well established, there is a lack of current, comprehensive, large-scale studies in Iraq that evaluate the extent of neonatal jaundice and document the range of risk factors of maternal, neonatal, and perinatal origin for the development of neonatal jaundice. The majority of studies conducted have focused on either the capital city, Baghdad, or the available studies are dated [19,20]. The Obstetrics and Pediatrics Hospital in Samawah, located in Al-Muthanna Governorate, is the primary referral centre for obstetric and paediatric patients in the region, and the majority of the populations served are urban or semi-urban. Identifying the local epidemiology of neonatal jaundice is essential in creating context-appropriate clinical guidelines, making evidence-based decisions regarding resource allocation for phototherapy units, designing preventive measures and education for health care workers and mothers.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to fill the knowledge gap on neonatal jaundice requiring phototherapy in Sabawah by determining the prevalence of neonatal jaundice in this population, defining the relationship between maternal, neonatal, and perinatal factors, and identifying the incidence of these factors in relation to neonatal jaundice. This information will allow for a deeper understanding of hyperbilirubinemia in Iraq and will provide evidence-based recommendations to conduct clinical practice and public health policy in an evidence-based way to

reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with severe neonatal jaundice and its complications.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

This is a cross-sectional, retrospective study using data from a hospital setting selected from within a city, Samawah, which serves as the primary obstetric and pediatric facility for the Al-Muthanna Governorate of southern Iraq. The site of the study, a general public facility, affords patients the ability to receive free obstetric, neonatal, and pediatric care. Additionally, the hospital delivers both in born patients that have been delivered at this hospital will also receive referrals of out-born patients from outside this facility who have been identified by other medical providers with complications of newly born infants, including infants with jaundice.

Sample Population

The subjects of the study are all live-born infants who were born at the hospital or who were admitted to the neonatal unit during the first 28 days of life for the management of jaundice from January 1, to December 31, 2022. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for final analysis included live-born infants who died after 24 hours and those whose medical records were incomplete for either bilirubin levels (if present), gestation (if born prematurely), or weight (where present).

Case Definition

A patient classified as “significant neonatal jaundice,” for the purposes of the study, has been given an initial diagnosis by virtue of their total serum bilirubin (TSB) equal to or greater than the AAP-defined phototherapy threshold of 2004. However, this diagnosis must also take into consideration whether any patient classified as “significant neonatal jaundice” presents with the mother’s hemolytic risk factors prior to or at delivery (after adjusting for gestational age of less than 38 weeks). All total serum bilirubins collected by the laboratory within the hospital were subject to measurement using the diazo method.

Sources of Data Collection

Data collection for the study utilized a variety of methods. Three (3) primary sources were utilized to identify subjects included within the study: birth registry records maintained by the hospital, maternal patient care records maintained by the hospital, and neonatal patient care records maintained by the hospital. The data abstraction form that was used to collect the information was structured and pre-tested. Each variable was then grouped according to the following:

Maternal Variables: Age, parity (1st time vs. multiple births), mode of delivery (spontaneous vs. c-section), gestational diabetes or hypertension in the mother,

blood group and Rh factor of the mother, and a child previously treated for jaundice or not.

Neonatal Variables: Sex, gestational age (< 37 weeks [preterm] vs. ≥ 37 weeks [term]), birth weight (< 2500g [low birth weight (LBW)] vs. ≥ 2500g), initiation type of feeding (exclusively breastfeeding, formula feed, or mixed); the presence of bruising or cephalohematoma at birth.

Jaundice-Specific Variables: Age (in days) when jaundice first appeared, the highest TSB level, age (in hours) of the highest TSB level, direct bilirubin level (if measured), hours of phototherapy, or if exchange transfusion was necessary. Neonates’ blood group and direct Coombs in/for ABO/Rh incompatibility will be collected as part of the etiology assessment; however, testing for glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency is not routinely performed; only if completed will it be assessed.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25.0 was used to enter and analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics (i.e., frequencies and percentages for categorical variables, means with SDs or medians with IQR for continuous variables depending on distribution) and the prevalence of significant jaundice in the sample will be determined by the calculation of the number of neonates who developed significant jaundice and needed treatment divided by the total number of live births during the study period, reported as a percentage.

Bivariate analyses to assess if an association exists between each of the independent variables and the outcome (significant jaundice). Chi-square tests will be used to analyze categorical variables (Fisher’s exact test will be used when appropriate). Multivariable binary logistic regression models will be developed, and independent risk factors associated with significant jaundice ($p < 0.1$) in the bivariate analysis will be identified while adjusting for potential confounding factors. The results of the logistic regression will be presented as adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI), with significance at $p < 0.05$ in the final model.

Ethics

The study approach has been reviewed and approved by both the Hospital Administration and the local Health Directorate. Because retrospective record reviews are used for this study, there was no requirement for informed consent. Anonymized study numbers will be assigned to all study participants to allow for the protection of confidentiality, and access to the study data will be limited to investigators who have obtained approval from the Principal Investigators to have access to the database.

Results

4,850 live births occurred at the Obstetrics and Pediatrics Hospital in Samawah during the study period with 4,782 neonatal participants (after applying

exclusion criteria) included in the final analysis. Of these, 682 neonates developed significant jaundice and required phototherapy, resulting in a period prevalence of 14.1%.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population (N=4,782)

Characteristic	Category	All Neonates (n=4782)	Jaundiced Neonates (n=682)	Non-Jaundiced Neonates (n=4100)	p-value
Neonatal Gender	Male	2470 (51.7%)	412 (60.4%)	2058 (50.2%)	<0.001
	Female	2312 (48.3%)	270 (39.6%)	2042 (49.8%)	
Gestational Age	Term (≥37 wks)	4320 (90.3%)	510 (74.8%)	3810 (92.9%)	<0.001
	Preterm (<37 wks)	462 (9.7%)	172 (25.2%)	290 (7.1%)	
Birth Weight	≥2500 g	4250 (88.9%)	510 (74.8%)	3740 (91.2%)	<0.001
	<2500 g (LBW)	532 (11.1%)	172 (25.2%)	360 (8.8%)	
Mode of Delivery	Vaginal	3250 (68.0%)	480 (70.4%)	2770 (67.6%)	0.152
	Cesarean Section	1532 (32.0%)	202 (29.6%)	1330 (32.4%)	
Maternal Age	≥20 years	4015 (84.0%)	520 (76.2%)	3495 (85.2%)	<0.001
	<20 years	767 (16.0%)	162 (23.8%)	605 (14.8%)	
Parity	Multipara	3100 (64.8%)	380 (55.7%)	2720 (66.3%)	<0.001
	Primipara	1682 (35.2%)	302 (44.3%)	1380 (33.7%)	

Table 2: Clinical Profile and Etiology of Jaundiced Neonates (n=682)

Parameter	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Type of Jaundice	Physiologic/Breastfeeding	533	78.2
	Pathological	149	21.8
Age at Onset	≤ 3 days	315	46.2
	> 3 days	367	53.8
Peak TSB (mg/dL)	Mean ± SD	16.8 ± 3.4	-
	Range	10.5 - 28.3	-
ABO Incompatibility	Positive (DAT+)	58	8.5
	Negative/Not Done	624	91.5
Rh Incompatibility	Positive	4	0.6
Exchange Transfusion	Required	11	1.6
G6PD Deficiency*	Tested (n=180)	22	(12.2 of tested)

Note: *G6PD testing was not universal; performed only in cases of severe, early-onset, or unexplained jaundice.

Table 3: Independent Risk Factors for Significant Neonatal Jaundice (Multivariable Logistic Regression)

Risk Factor	Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR)	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Preterm (<37 wks)	3.45	2.67 - 4.46	<0.001
Low Birth Weight (<2500g)	2.89	2.18 - 3.83	<0.001
Male Gender	1.52	1.25 - 1.85	<0.001
Primiparity	1.48	1.21 - 1.80	<0.001
Maternal Age <20 years	1.92	1.45 - 2.55	<0.001
Sibling with Jaundice History	2.95	2.15 - 4.05	<0.001

The logistic regression model confirmed these factors as independent predictors after controlling for others. ABO incompatibility was a significant risk in bivariate analysis but was not included in the final multivariable model as it was part of the etiological assessment of cases rather than a universal screening variable for the entire cohort.

Discussion

In this research, a 14.1% prevalence rate of significant neonatal jaundice which needs phototherapy came to

light, being near the midpoint of ranges identified by other studies conducted in this area [17,18,21]. Research conducted in Iran shows the prevalence of neonatal jaundice has been both low (11.5%) and high (up to 35%), while studies conducted in Saudi Arabia and Egypt reported much lower rates (between 8% and 20%) [22,23]. As such, this study validates neonatal jaundice as a common problem in the Iraqi hospital system and as a condition that consumes a substantial number of resources. Additionally, global literature

indicates that three-quarters (78.2%) of the cases observed in this study are classified as either physiologic or related to breastfeeding, demonstrating that most neonates with jaundice have been shown to be healthy in nature; however, 21.8% may have identifiable pathologic causes which require further investigation for diagnostic purposes [1,24].

Based on previous studies and the established pathophysiologic principles, prematurity (AOR=3.45) and low birth weight (AOR=2.89) were found to be the most important independent risk factors [9,10]. Immature hepatic enzymes, in particular the UDP-glucuronosyltransferase enzyme found in the liver, significantly impair jaundice conjugation and excretion for premature and LBW infants [6]. Additionally, these newborns frequently have difficulty feeding, resulting in significant caloric deprivation and/or dehydration. This negatively impacts their jaundice because they have an increased enterohepatic reabsorption of bilirubin [25]. These findings warrant careful monitoring of bilirubin levels in this vulnerable population, potentially using hour-specific nomograms, prior to the onset of clinical jaundice [26].

The increased risk of jaundice associated with males (AOR=1.52) has been reported consistently throughout the literature [13,27]. The exact mechanisms for these differences are unclear but could be related to hormonal effects on the breakdown of bilirubin or a higher number of red blood cells in males. Because males have some biological characteristics that predispose them to developing hyperbilirubinemia, physicians should have slightly more suspicion about hyperbilirubinemia in male infants.

There were many factors related to the mother and delivery that contributed to hyperbilirubinemia in infants. For example, being a first-time mother (primipara) was identified as one of the top risk factors (AOR=1.48). Being a first-time mother is often associated with breastfeeding-related jaundice [28]. First-time mothers sometimes may experience delayed lactogenesis and difficulties establishing adequate breastfeeding, resulting in poor intake, weight loss, and dehydration in the infant—all of which are contributors to high levels of bilirubin [29]. The findings also support the relationship with having a young mother (<20 years; AOR=1.92). Adolescent mothers may have a lack of antenatal education, lower socioeconomic status, and less support, which can further complicate breastfeeding issues [33]. Therefore, this points to an area of intervention for mothers who are first-time mothers and for mothers who are young; specifically, that they should receive culturally sensitive support and education (breastfeeding support, counselling, etc.) during the immediate postpartum period. Initiatives that focus on frequent breastfeeding and reviewing the infant's latch may help reduce the

number of infants developing significant hyperbilirubinemia [31].

Additionally, a family history of hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn's previous sibling was a significant risk factor for developing hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn (AOR=2.95), which supports genetic studies, which show that there appear to be familial polymorphisms in bilirubin-metabolising genes, including UGT1A1 and OATP2 [32]. The high frequency of relatedness in the Iraqi population raises the chances of a person inheriting undesirable genetic combinations [15]. Thus, the potential for a subject to inherit these genetic combinations can be determined using inexpensive and easily accessible historical data will allow the focus of each of the anticipated risks through maternal admission and prenatal delivery assessments. If the mother has had these types of assessments done, the newborn will be placed into a high-risk group for closer monitoring [8].

ABO blood type incompatibility in 8.5% of babies who had jaundice confirms that ABO hemolytic disease is an identifiable cause of jaundice; however, only 0.6% had Rh disease due to successful ABCD prophylaxis even in a limited resource area [11]. The management of ABO hemolytic disease continues to be clinically relevant for those who are diagnosed. A significant barrier to successful diagnostic assessment is the absence of laboratory assessment for G6PD deficiency; therefore, individuals found susceptible to G6PD deficiency demonstrate the importance of resolving the condition before its onset. Also, the absence of universal laboratory screening further complicates the detection of G6PD deficiency due to lack of education in families regarding the importance of avoiding exposure to oxidative stressors.

The study was limited in that it was a retrospective chart review; therefore, the possibility exists that there were information bias related to the accuracy of documentation of infant breastfeeding status and the complete familial history of the infant. Additionally, documenting the cause of jaundice may incorrectly classify some infants due to an incomplete evaluation; two likely sources of misclassification are underdiagnosed bacterial sepsis and metabolic disease. The study analysed the population at a single institution and therefore, the prevalence rates calculated will not be generalizable to the Iraqi population; however, the risk factors identified should be similar in both populations. Additionally, although the 2004 AAP clinical guidelines are appropriate for current clinical practice, the 2004 clinical thresholds for measuring jaundice severity differ from more contemporary recommendations [33].

This study provides an understanding of the epidemiology of jaundice in Iraq. The epidemiology of jaundice, its prevalence, and risk factors demonstrate

that adequate resources need to be allocated for clinical and public health intervention initiatives in order to meet the needs of patients who develop jaundice.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate an overall high rate of jaundice in neonates needing treatment in Iraq. Additionally, risk factors that significantly contribute to adverse fetal outcomes (i.e., prematurity, low birth weight, male sex, first-time mother, maternal age, and history of jaundice) may be modified to improve surveillance for these infants. Improvements in the availability of quality prenatal care, the availability of resources to support breastfeeding, and a consistent method for assessing the risk status of infants following delivery will help to improve the recognition and treatment of jaundice and help reduce the incidence of severe hyperbilirubinemia and neurological complications among these patients.

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